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Doctoral Abstracts

Book Reviews

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Contents

Survival of the Vulnerable: Strategies Employed by Small to Medium Enterprises in Zimbabwe to Survive an Economic Crises

Zirima Hebert, Nyanga Takupiwa, Mupani Honest, Chifamba Ephraim

1-6

Global Financial Crisis and Indian Economy: Causes & Consequences

Dr. Mohmed Amin Mir

7-24

Mobile Phone Usage in Bangladesh: The Effects of Attitude Towards Behaviour and Subjective Norm

Md. Shah Azam, Nasrin Lubna

25-34

Mood Effects on Celebrity Credibility Evaluation – A Comparison of Emerging and Matured Sport Celebrities

Dr. S. Sundar, Dr. R. Venkatesakumar

35-44

Effects of the Professional Mobility and the Intentional Factors on the Entrepreneurial Act of the Tunisian Public Civil Servant

Hammami Hajer

45-55

Customer is the King...A Microscopic View into Selection of Tea Brand in Nagpur & Wardha

Dr. Gayathri Band, Dr. Mrs. Neeta V Shah

56-67

Employee Perception of Service Quality : A Comparison between Public Sector Banks and Private Sector Banks in Karnataka, India

Linda Nalini Daniel, R. Alamelumangai

68-78

Buyer Behaviour Patterns and Satisfaction Trends of Commercial Vehicles owners in Replacement of Tyres

K. Natarajan, Dr. K. Soundararajan and Dr. J. Jayakrishnan

79-86

Doctoral Abstracts

Book Reviews

87-89

90-97

BUYER BEHAVIOUR PATTERNS AND SATISFACTION TRENDS OF COMMERCIAL VEHICLES OWNERS IN REPLACEMENT OF TYRES

K. Natarajan, Dr. K. Soundararajan and Dr. J. Jayakrishnan

Abstract

The Indian Tyre industry derives its demand from the automobile industry. While OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturers) market off take is dependent on the new vehicle sales. Replacement market demand depends on the total population of vehicle on road, road conditions, vehicle scraping rules, overloading norms for trucks, average life of tyres and prevalence of tyre retreading. The main category of tyre produced in the country is that of Truck & Bus tyres. Indian tyre industry, comprising of 40 companies (47 factories) in the organized and unorganized sector, account for over 80% of industry turnover and have a well diversified product-mix and presence in all three major segments, i.e., Replacement Market, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM's) and Exports. This paper focused to study the purchasing behaviour of Heavy and Light Commercial vehicles owners in Replacement tyres.

Keywords – Consumer satisfaction, Replacement tyres, Commercial vehicles

Introduction

Customer satisfaction is widely used in evaluating business performance both internally and externally. Internally, customer satisfaction is used to monitor performance, allocate resources, and compensate employees. Externally, customers satisfaction provides information to a wide range of interest group, including customers, competitors, and public policy makers. Basic psychology process play an important role in understanding how consumers actually make their buying decision and the key interest to the marketers is the major information sources to which the consumer will turn and the relative influence each will have in the subsequent purchase decision. These information sources fell into four groups. (1) Personal – family, friends, neighbours, acquaintances. (2) Commercial – Advertising, web sites, sales persons,

dealers, packaging, displays. (3) Public – man media, consumer – rally organization. (4) Experiential – Handling, examining, uses the product. Though gathering information, the consumer learns about competing brands and their features. Some brands will meet initial buying criteria, as the consumer gathers more information's, only a few will remain strong contenders. The consumer makes a final choice from a set.

Indian tyre industry, comprising of 40 companies (47 factories) in the organized and unorganized sector, can be divided into two tiers; Tier – I player (top 5 tyre companies such as Apollo, Ceat, Good Year, JK Tyres and MRF) account for over 80% of industry turnover and have a well diversified product-mix and presence in all three major segments, such as, Replacement Market, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM's) and Exports. Tier – II companies are small in size, mainly concentrating on production of small tyres (for two / three – wheelers, etc), tubes & flaps and the replacement market. The industry has negligible market share in the commercial vehicles tyre category and is around 20% in the two wheelers category. Apollo, Ceat, Good year, JK Tyres

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and MRF are the dominating tyre Industry in India. Replacement market is one of the more sought-after markets by Tyre players, since the margins are better compared to those of OEM's (who are relatively few in number and have a huge bargaining power). Replacement demand, which comes from existing automobiles, has been increasing for sometime now and is expected to do the same, going forward. Replacement tyres varies across categories, due to different life-spans of tyres, which depends on reasons like, Road condition, Load carried, Distance traveled and Re-treading.

Literature Review

Research has long established that perception of product quality can be influenced by various attributes, such as brand name (Dawar and Parker 1994; Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal 1991), Price (Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal 1991; Rao and Monroe 1989) and Product appearance (Dawar and Parker 1994). Influence is inferred the person acts in such a way as to change the behaviour of another in an intended manner. Influence involves actions by family members that made a difference during the decision process. Relative influence means it is relative to the influence of other family members Brinberg, David and Nancy Schwenk. (1985). The research has shown that satisfaction for a product is also related to how customers are satisfied by their buying experience (Pettijohn CE et al. 2002). The firms marketing success generally depends on the dealers, because these persons are the ones who have the most direct influence on the customers. In this sense, estimating customers judgment about their "buying experience" and evaluating the aspects that influence their perception of this service most, could help marketing the product a success. Translation of average satisfaction relating into repurchase behaviour may vary if consumers have different thresholds or tolerance levels with respect to repurchase. Given the same rating, consumer with lower thresholds may be more likely to repurchase the brand than those higher thresholds (Vikas Mittal and Wagner A. Kamakura 2001).

Richard N. Cardozo (1965) found that customer evaluation of the performance of a product was

influenced by expectations concerning the product under certain conditions. Subjects use their expectations as guidelines against which they evaluated the product. According to Cardozo when the purchase confirms the consumer's expectations, reinforcement takes place. When expectations are not confirmed, however cognitive inconsistency develops and the consumer is likely to reduce the dissonance by evaluating the product fails to measure up to the consumers expectation or guidelines for evaluation the result may be no initial sale, no repeat sale or unfavourable word-of-mouth communication. Ganapathi et al., (2008) stated that the purchase is normally influenced by many, including the customer's perceptions and behavior. Hence, it is as complicated as human mind. It becomes imperative for the marketers to understand the customer's behavior and perception before developing marketing strategy. Strong competition in the market has also resulted in many companies fighting for a place in the consumers mind.

So, it is important that to study the consumer's perceptions and behavior of the customer which will give us a feed back on how the marketing strategies can be worked. It is found that the various features of services such as minimum waiting time, respectful, friendly atmosphere, helpful to the customer, value for money etc., can attract the prospective buyer. Purchasing behaviour involves complicated services of stimulus and response. These stimuli are called as motives. These motives may be expressed or unexpressed and are based upon deep seated needs or more openly felt desires when someone purchase something, the person psychologically satisfies both a need and a want. Pratyush Tripathi and Satish Kr. Singh. (2012). Modern purchasers want to know not only about the product features but also to know how and why the product will benefit them. They look not only for what a product can do but also what they mean.

The overall tyre performance is based on five factors (in order of importance) appearance, durability, ride, traction, and handling (J.D. Power 2005) "tyre manufacturers not only need to provide better tyre performance but also need to focus on aligning strategies to customer expectations so they

can provide a satisfactory tyre ownership experience". The study finds that the absence of tyre problems contributes to greater level of satisfaction and strongly influences customers perceptions of the tyre brand. Furthermore, problem-free tyre experience lead a higher degree of advocacy and loyalty for the tyre brand. Drivers of customer satisfaction and loyalty at the industry levels are – expectation, image, product quality and service quality (Anne Martensen et. al. 2000) expectation have no or only a very limited impact on satisfaction and loyalty. Image is the main drivers for customer satisfaction. Service becomes a more important driver for bank customer loyalty. But image still has the largest impact on loyalty.

Objectives of the study

Customer satisfaction has received considerable attention from researchers in marketing. Customer satisfaction is generally construed to be a post consumption evaluation depends on perceived quality or value, expectation, and confirmation/disconfirmation. The study is aimed at to know the satisfaction level of replacement tyre customers in Light and Heavy commercial vehicles in Chidambaram Town and to find out the brand preference and factors influencing the customer satisfaction during their replacement decision.

Research Design

To study the purchasing behaviour of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres Quantitative research study was done as descriptive information was required over there. The researcher used survey method using schedules. The researcher personally involved in this research and collected primary data from the respondent. The respondents are - Owners of Bus, Trucks, and Light Commercial Vehicles.

Data Collection Tool

Data collection instruments were developed as a part of the study's total research design to systematize the collection of data and to ensure that all the respondents are asked the same questions and

in the same order. A Schedule was designed to know about the Purchase behaviour of Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres. Schedule designed includes both substantive questions that are relevant to Heavy and Light commercial vehicles owners on Replacement tyres.

Sampling and data collection

The sampling plan addresses three questions: Whom to survey (the sampling unit), how many to survey (the sample size) and how to select them (the sampling procedure). The size of the sample is dependent both on the size of the budget and on the degree of confidence that the researcher wants to place in the findings. Here a sample size of 100 customers was selected throughout Chidambaram Town using the Stratified Random Sampling technique. Various types of data analysis tools were used to analyze the data collected by the schedule, descriptive and one way ANOVA.

Analysis and discussion

After all the customers were surveyed, i.e., a sample size of 100, the analysis was done on the basis of their responses in the following way:

Table -1 explains the experience, sources of awareness of the various brands of tyres and awareness of brands in years. Experience of respondent plays an important role in their purchasing behaviour of replacement tyres. Among the respondent of this study about 65 percent are having

Table – 1 PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Factors		Frequency and Percent
Experience	Up to 5 years	11.0
	6-10 years	11.0
	11-15 years	13.0
	15 years & above	65.0
Awareness through	Experience	98.0
	Friends	02.0
Awareness of Brands in years	Up to 5 years	11.0
	6-10 years	11.0
	11-15 years	13.0
	15 years & above	65.0

Source: Primary Data - computed

experience of more than 15 years. Among the respondent 98 percent of them are aware of the brands through experience and rest of the 2 percent of the respondent are aware of the brands through friends. (Pettijohn CE et al. 2002) has shown that satisfaction for a product is related to how customers are satisfied by their "buying experience". It shows that experience of a person place an important influencing factor to the purchase of replacement tyres. About 65 percent of the respondent having experience of 15 years and above and 13 percent of the respondent having experience of 11-15 years experience, and only 11 percent of the respondent having the experience of up to 5 years. (Gulorsen and Robert John 1994) examined the relative impact of four variables: product, information availability, experience and judgment ability. They were identified as having the major influence on consumer information. He also reported that experience, information availability, interaction of product type and experience had a significant influence on the amount of search behaviour for goods.

Table- 2 shows the experience of the customers in various sectors of the commercial vehicles. Experience of respondent plays an important role in their purchasing behaviour of replacement tyres. Among the respondent of this study about 65 percent of the respondent having experience of more than 15 years. Gulorsen and Robert John (1994) reported that experience, information availability, interaction of product type and experience had a significant influence on the amount of search behaviour for goods.

TABLE – 2 AWARENESS OF BRANDS IN YEARS

Awareness in years	Frequency and Percent
Up to 5 years	11.0
6-10 years	11.0
11-15 years	13.0
15 years & above	65.0

Source – Primary Data computed

The researcher considered eight major brands of tyres available in the market for the present study such as MRF tyre, JK Tyre, Apollo tyre, Bridgestone tyre, Ceat tyre, Good Year tyre, Vikrant tyre and Birla tyre.

From the analysis it is concluded that out of 100 respondents, 48 percent of the consumer prefer to buy MRF tyre for their replacement and followed the JK tyres with 36 percent of the replacement buyer (Table 3). It shows that when compared with other tyres, these two are qualitative and satisfy the customers.

TABLE – 3 BRAND OF TYRES PREFERRED TO BUY

Brand	Frequency and Percentage
MRF Tyre	48.0
JK Tyre	36.0
Apollo Tyre	6.0
Bridgestone Tyre	5.0
Ceat Tyre	2.0
Good Year Tyre	1.0
Vikrant Tyre	1.0
Birla Tyre	1.0
Total	100.0

Source – Primary Data computed

Table - 4 explains the reasons for purchasing selected brands by the respondent. Price of the tyre is the major reason to select a replacement of tyre followed by Brands already fitted, the manufacturer's recommendation and distributor recommendation is the least influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. The study (J D Power 2009) reveals that customer satisfaction with original equipment tyres has a strong impact on brand loyalty and advocacy for replacement tyres. Customer who are highly satisfied are twice as likely to recommend or repurchase their current tyre brand when buying replacement tyres. The owners those who are having up to 5 years of experience are highly favoured with Price, Reliability Performance, Road Grip, Depth, Rolling Resistance, Driver Recommendation, Quick availability of Tyres. Above 15 years experienced owners are influenced by Safety, Manufacturer Recommendation, and Distributor Recommendation for the purchase of Replacement Tyres. The New entrant is interested to purchase of replacement tyre because of Speed of delivery and Brand already fitted.

Respondents are asked to rate their purchase behaviour of Replacement of tyres based on their

Table – 4 REASON TO PURCHASE A SELECT BRAND

Factors	Mean	Std. Deviation
Price	3.57	1.02
Reliability	2.87	1.37
Performance	3.18	1.29
Safety	2.50	1.10
Road Grip	2.89	1.30
Depth	3.09	1.33
Rolling Resistance	3.15	1.21
Delivery	3.00	1.10
Driver Recommendation	2.40	1.68
Quick Availability	2.61	1.10
Manufacturer Recommendation	2.18	1.62
Brand already fitted	3.26	1.36
Distributor Recommendation	2.39	1.56

Source – Primary Data computed

experience. The data are grouped based on experience and calculated mean and standard deviation value for each factors with respect to experience. The value is displayed in the Table – 5. From the mean value it is observed that buyer having experience of up to 5 years are satisfied with the price of Replacement tyres than others and they are also prefer for quick availability of Replacement tyres. Those who have more than 15 years are influenced by Reliability, Performance, Safety, Road Grip, Depth, Rolling resistance.

Findings

From the study it is found that about 65 percent of the respondents having experience of more than 15 years. Experience of a person plays an important role of influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. About 65 percent of the respondent know the brands for past 15 years and 13 percent of the respondents are heard the brand of 11-15 years, only 11 percent of the respondents are aware of the brand for 5 years. Price of tyre shows the major reason influencing the purchase behaviour followed by Brands already fitted Manufacturers recommendation and distributors recommendation is the least influencing factor for the purchase of replacement tyres. Price factor mostly influences the respondent whose experience is up to 5 years and

the respondent state that the price of the tyre is moderately good, than the respondent whose experience is 6-10 years. About 48 percent of the respondent prefers to buy MRF tyres followed by JK tyres with 36 percent of the respondent.

Suggestions

All level of experienced owners perceived similar level of opinion towards Replacement of tyres, it shows that, the owners are having less involvement with the purchase of replacement tyres. So, owners should be trained and create awareness towards importance of purchase in Replacement Tyres. The tyre manufacturers to invite the owners and explain the merits of the Replacement of Tyres, so it will help to capture the market share and increase sales volume. Based on the study, it is understand MRF and JK Tyres are the dominating brand. So, MRF and JK tyres can maintain the same level. And also other players like Apollo, Ceat, Bridgestone etc., should promote their brand with attractive scheme like price discounts, speed of delivery, credit mode, and free maintenance etc. From the study, the manufacturer recommendation is not an influencing factor of the respondent. So, vehicle manufacturers should use customer expected Brand, it will strengthen customer and owners relationship. It can help to increase volume of sales as what vehicle manufacturers can recommend.

TABLE - 5 FACTORS INFLUENCING REPLACEMENT OF TYRES BASED ON EXPERIENCE

Factor	Experience	Mean	Std. Deviation
Price	Up to 5 years	3.77	0.666
	6-10 years	3.72	0.646
	11-15 years	3.15	0.987
	15 years & above	3.66	0.816
			2.60
Reliability	Up to 5 years	2.60	1.184
	6-10 years	3.18	1.601
	11-15 years	3.00	1.683
	15 years & above	3.33	1.414
Performance	Up to 5 years	2.90	1.300
	6-10 years	3.30	1.315
	11-15 years	2.78	1.188
	15 years & above	3.55	1.236
Safety	Up to 5 years	2.22	0.666
	6-10 years	2.54	1.439
	11-15 years	2.46	1.126
	15 years & above	2.78	1.188
Road Grip	Up to 5 years	2.74	1.262
	6-10 years	2.81	1.401
	11-15 years	2.92	1.441
	15 years & above	3.55	1.509
Depth	Up to 5 years	2.81	1.401
	6-10 years	2.82	1.280
	11-15 years	3.61	1.388
	15 years & above	3.77	1.394
Rolling Resistance	Up to 5 years	3.00	2.213
	6-10 years	3.46	1.285
	11-15 years	3.21	1.188
	15 years & above	3.66	1.322
Quick Availability	Up to 5 years	3.22	1.301
	6-10 years	2.36	0.924
	11-15 years	2.38	0.960
	15 years & above	2.66	1.177
Brand already fitted	Up to 5 years	3.77	1.394
	6-10 years	3.09	1.513
	11-15 years	3.30	1.493
	15 years & above	3.17	1.352

Source - Primary Data computed

Conclusion

From the study it is concluded that there are different factors influencing the owners of the Heavy and Light Commercial Vehicles in replacement tyres, among the factors Brand already fitted with the vehicle plays an important factors in replacement of tyres and followed by the performance of tyres. The study also reveals that the owners purchase behaviour of Replacement tyres.

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FUNDED PROJECT SYNOPSIS

The Department of Business Administration is happy to publish a section of project Synopses to keep "Annamalai International Journal of Business Studies and Research" (AIJBSR) readers abreast with completed research projects. This section will also inform readers about the funded projects, funding agencies, and the grants received.

Principal Investigators who have recently completed their research projects (within the past three years) are encouraged to follow the guidelines below.

Guidelines

1. Synopsis of completed projects that belong to the Social Sciences discipline will be considered for publication. AIJBSR reserves the final right on publication decision of any submission.
2. Only after the completion of the project and report submission to the funding agency the synopses can be sent with proper acknowledgement.
3. Synopsis not exceeding 2500 words (maximum 10 pages, one and half line spacing, including diagram, charts, tables, references).
4. Each submission should include the following details:

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Address of the Agency :

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